

LECTURERS' PERCEPTION OF UTILIZING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR INSTRUCTIONAL SERVICE DELIVERY IN BUSINESS EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN DELTA STATE UNIVERSITY, ABRAKA.

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Digital Technologies Instructional Delivery, Business Education programme

Abstract: *The Study was conducted to ascertain lecturers' perception of utilizing digital technologies for Instructional Service Delivery in Business Education programme in Delta State University, Abraka. Nigerian. Using a survey, design, the researcher utilized a sample of 24 lecturers from a department of Business Education and Institute of Education. This sample size constituted the population. Four research questions guided the study. Instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire which consisted of 43 items and validated by experts in the field of measurement and evaluation. Responses on the instrument were measured on a 4-point rating scale. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability coefficient of 0.87. Descriptive statistics of mean, frequencies and percentages were used to answer the research questions. The findings shows that lecturers' level of awareness of digital technology tools. is low, it was recommended that government owned institutions should organize training for lecturers to acquaint them of digital tools used for instructional service delivery*

Introduction

In Nigeria, knowledge has been considered as a literacy tool for development of workforce. To this affirmation, several policies have been made in order to strengthen educational environment to meet up with its policies, goals and objectives. One of these policies is introduction of Business Education programme for the training of individuals and those who wants to join teaching

profession. Business education programme as an aspect of in-training programme which is given to people who are require it for their general education and upgrading or to enable them to obtain higher certificated or professional qualification. In this context, Business education programme could be defined as an educational programme given to individuals who intends to further their

Dr. (Mrs.) Val-Ossai, Marilyn Unonwa and Dr. Edionwe Nosakhare

education with responsibility of teaching and research. (Edionwe, 2022)

According to Okoro and Nwakaire (2022), Business education program in Nigeria is organized and ran during academic sessions to avail those who are seeking teaching and research the opportunity to participate as well as to afford serving teachers the opportunity of improving themselves academically and professionally. This Business education program offer courses that have been accredited for the Faculty of Education and its objectives are in line with the main objectives of program. Basically, the program could be said to be very important just like the other teachers training.

The importance of teaching program in the development of teachers cannot be overemphasized. Edionwe, (2021) opine that the Business education degree program is at achieving virtually all its stated objectives such as encouraging continuous academic growth of producing teachers, improving competence and enhance quality of teachers. However, Business education programs are designed to produce teachers to; teach chosen courses, infuse creativity into teaching, supervision research and learning. Utilize specialize training to give leadership in critical assessment and development of self-discipline, among others. Apart from these, Okoro, (2022,) observed that it is much cheaper to produce graduate teachers through the Business education degree program. Despite the great goals and objectives of Business education program, this program has got its share of criticism. Several researchers

have classified this program to be a crashed program due to the time allotted for the program. Hence, some shortcomings include: entry qualifications, course duration and reduction in the scope of course content required to designed cover lesson topics in a particular course in a given period. The duration of the Business education program raises serious concern as to whether students actually cover required knowledge in their respective areas of specialization. This therefore increase doubt as to whether the Business education program is achieving its stated objective of promoting teacher effectiveness in Nigeria education system. Consequently, Okoro, (2023) stated that some employers of labor have been found to discriminate between products of various Business education programs.

However, globalization through Digital Technology has made it possible for learning to place without the physical contact between teacher and student. Digital Technology is an umbrella term that includes any communication device, encompassing radio, television, cell phones, computer and network hardware, satellite systems and so on, as the various services and application with them such as video conferencing and distance learning. This versatile instrument has the capability not only to engaging students in instructional activities to increase their learning, but of helping them to solve complex problems to enhance cognitive and psychological skills.

Digitalization encompasses radio and television, as well as newer digital technologies such as

computers, the Internet have been touted as potentially powerful enabling tools for educational change and reform. Digital are relevant in the development of human mental resources which allow people to both successfully apply the existing knowledge and produce new knowledge. Furthermore, Digital facilities in education have help improve memory retention, increase motivation and generally deepens understanding. Digital tools can also be used to promote collaborative learning, including role playing, group problem solving activities and articulated projects. Today, laptops perform a host of functions in teaching and learning as many nations adding computer literacy, reading and writing literacy as skills student will need for succeeding in a technologically developed world.

An aspect of education that digital tools are utilized globally today is distance learning. Robinson (2008) reported that the use of distance education and digital tools has the potential to distribute opportunities for learning wider and equitably across the teaching force. Similarly, Jimoh (2013) is of the view that open and distance learning together with appropriate digital tools has the powerful potential to impact significantly on education content and delivery in teacher development in Africa. Digital tools that are interactive, electronic, and computer-based are utilized for distributing instructions and facilitating communication between learners and teachers as in video-conferencing, audio-conferencing, electronic mails, or most computer-based discussions. In line with this,

Digital tools can be relevant in education through the use of internet, CD ROM sources, database or spreadsheet and communication technologies (e-mail and video conferencing).

However, several factors have been stated to as factors that affect utilization of in education. Studies investigated the challenges affecting the use of digital tools in universities. Attitude is a predisposition to respond favorably to an objects, person or event (Okoro 2022). Moreso, factors that influence successful integration of digital tools into teaching are teachers' attitude and beliefs towards technology. Therefore, theories about the value of technology greatly enhanced teachers' perceptions about the effectiveness of technology for service delivery. Research has shown that teachers' attitude towards technology influence their acceptance of the usefulness of technology and its integration into instructional delivery Most times, the attitude of a person in utilizing laptops could be based on the person's level of competence. High-level experience teachers have with computer, the more like that they will show positive attitudes towards teachers' computer competence is a major predictor of integrating digital tools in teaching.

Digital tools competence is defined as being able to handle a wide range of varying tools applications for various purpose Teachers' Digital competence has been noted as one of the factors affecting the use computer by lecturers in schools. Most secondary school teachers lack the skills to fully utilize technology in curriculum implementation hence the traditional chalk and

duster approach still dominates in most of educational pedagogy

Over the years, several research works are being carried out on Digital tools. Opataye (2012)) carried out a study to ascertain science teachers' perception and readiness for e-learning instructional delivery in secondary schools in South west, Nigeria. Employing a survey design and a sample of 250 science teachers, the study found teachers to have positive perception towards utilizing e-learning in instructional delivery. In another study by Adedayo (2021) to determine lecturers' awareness of digital tools for instruction, result showed that lecturers had awareness of the usefulness of digital tools such as desktop computers, laptops, iPads, smartphones and others.

In a similar study, Oladosun (2012) conducted a study to determine basic technology teachers' awareness and attitude towards the use of digital tools for instruction in Lagos State. The study found teachers to have positive attitude towards utilizing digital tools for instruction but lack knowledge of how to integrated digital tools in instructional process. Similarly, Study to find out teachers' usage and perception of digital tools in Social Studies in Turkey found teachers to be willing to employ digital tools in instruction but lacking the basic training on how to integrate digital tools in instruction.

Furthermore, objective of determining lecturers' perception of integrating ICT in teaching and learning. The result showed that the lecturers had positive attitude and higher level of use of ICT in instructional process. To ascertain

lecturers' attitude towards the integration of digital tools in the curriculum found that lecturers had positive attitude towards its integration in the curriculum although they were not highly used in the instructional process. To determine teachers' perception towards integration of i digital tools to implement blended learning in universities as, result showed that teachers had positive perception towards blended learning with integration of digital tools

Statement of the Problem

The crave for qualification in Nigeria and the need for graduates to be relevant for promotion in the teaching profession, teachers who were not privileged to acquire higher qualification before employment do that while in service. This why the Nigerian government introduced higher program that can serve as a means of educating mostly teachers without interfering with academic session. However, this program has been criticized by some researchers to be a crashed program.

The quality teachers in the university system are trained through sandwich/part-time program This is as a result of the inappropriate time allotted for the program based on the fact that most students affected the ability of students to remember previous semester's work. This is worrisome owing to the fact the quality of graduates depends on the quality of teachers. However, technology has made it easier for students to learn even from their homes. Like the Nigerian Open University program and other related learning programs. It is of note that these

Dr. (Mrs.) Val-Ossai, Marilyn Unonwa and Dr. Edionwe Nosakhare

programs are successful. Therefore, the introduction of Digital tools can help in improving the performance of students. But the question is; what will be the level of acceptance by lecturers who will utilize these digital tools? It is against this backdrop that the researcher deemed it fit to examine lecturers' perception of utilizing Digital Technology for instructional service delivery in Business education program. In Delta State University, Abraka.

Purpose of study.

The purpose of the study was to ascertain lecturers' perception of utilizing Digital Technology in instructional service delivery in Business Education, Delta State University. Specifically, the study intended: to,

1. Ascertain the level of awareness of digital Technology tools for instructional delivery among lecturers in Business Education, Delta State University
2. Find out the level of knowledge on digital tools for instructional service delivery among lecturers in Business Education, Delta State University
3. Determine instructional theories lecturers perceive could be employed in enhancing instructional delivery with ICT in Business Education, Delta State University
4. Find out the opinion of lecturers towards utilizing Digital tools for instructional service delivery in Business Education, Delta State University, Abraka.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of digital tools for instructional delivery among lecturers

in Business Education, Delta State University Abraka?

2. What is the level of knowledge of how to utilize digital tools for instructional delivery among lecturers in Business Education, Delta State University Abraka?

3. What instructional theories do lecturers perceive could be employed in enhancing instructional delivery with digital in Business Education, Delta State University Abraka

4. What is the opinion of lecturers towards utilizing digital tools for instructional delivery in Business Education, Delta State University, Abraka.

Methodology

The study employed a survey design with a sample size of 24 lecturers of Business Education, Delta State University. The sample size constitutes 48% of the population. Instrument used for the study was questionnaire titled "Lecturers' Perception of Using digital Tools in Instructional Delivery (LPUITT)" towards comprising 43 items divided into four sections with each section addressing each research question. Responses on section A, B and D were rated on a four-point rating scale with cut of mean 2.50 while section C was in form of a checklist. The instrument was validated by experts in the field of educational Psychology and measurement and evaluation. A reliability coefficient of 0.87% was obtained for the instrument through Cronbach Alpha. Research question one, two and four were answered using descriptive statistics of mean.

Research question three was answered using percentages and frequencies.

Research Question 1: What is the level of awareness of Digital tools for instructional service delivery among lecturers in Business Education, Delta State University?

Results

Table 1: lecturers’ awareness of Digital tools for instructional service delivery (N=24)

S/N	Digital tools	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	M	Decision
1	Wiki	1	6	11	10	1.93	LE
2	Blog	1	4	7	16	1.64	LE
3	Instant messaging	1	5	7	15	1.71	LE
4	Whiteboard	18	6	2	2	3.43	HE
5	Virtual agenda	1	4	18	15	1.68	LE
6	Forum	1	8	13	6	2.14	LE
7	Chat	1	19	8	0	2.75	HE
8	Collaborative	2	10	14	2	2.43	LE
9	Authoring tool	0	5	6	17	1.57	LE
10	Website training resources	2	6	9	11	1.96	LE
11	DVD-ROM	7	14	6	1	2.96	HE
12	Web-conference system	2	10	10	6	2.29	LE
13	Videoconference system	2	10	16	0	2.50	HE
14	Mobile social media setting	3	7	4	14	1.96	LE

Source: Field survey, 2026.

Table one, shows that lecturers had awareness of whiteboard, chat, DVD-ROM and videoconferencing to a high extent. This is evident in the mean response of 3.43, 2.75, 2.96 and 2.50 respectively. Their awareness of wiki, blog, instant measuring, virtual agenda, forum, collaborative learning, authoring tool, websites training resources, web-conferencing and mobile social media setting as information and

communication technology tools for instructional delivery was low as indicated in the mean response ranging from 1.57 to 2.43.

Research Question 2:

What is the level of knowledge on utilizing Digital tools for instructional service delivery among lecturers in t Business Education, Delta State University?

Table 2: Lecturers knowledge of Digital tools for instructional Service delivery

S/N	Digital tools	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	M	Decision
1	Wiki	0	4	11	13	1.68	LE
2	Blog	0	1	12	15	1.50	LE
3	Instant messaging	1	2	9	16	1.57	LE
4	Whiteboard	14	8	3	3	3.18	HE
5	Virtual agenda	1	5	7	15	1.71	LE
6	Forum	1	8	12	7	2.11	LE
7	Chat	2	15	6	5	2.50	HE
8	Collaborative	1	6	13	8	2.00	LE
9	Authoring tool	0	3	11	14	1.61	LE
10	Website	1	5	5	17	1.64	LE
11	DVD-ROM	6	14	4	4	2.79	HE
12	Web-conference	1	4	13	10	1.86	LE
13	Videoconference	1	2	21	4	2.00	LE
14	Social media	2	3	7	16	1.68	LE

Source: Field survey, 2026.

Table two, shows that the lecturers had knowledge of utilizing whiteboard, chat and DVD-ROM for instructional service delivery to a high extent as evident in the respective mean responses of 3.18, 2.50 and 2.79. They however, had knowledge of using wiki, blog instant messaging, virtual agenda, forum, collaborative learning, authoring tool, websites training resources, videoconferencing, and web-

conferencing and social media to a low extent as indicated by mean response ranging from 1.50 to 2.11

Research Question 3: What instructional theories do lecturers perceive could be employed in enhancing instructional service delivery with Digital in Business Education, Delta State University?

Table 3: Lecturers’ perception of instructional Theories for Digital tools-enhanced instructional service delivery (N=24)

S/N	Digital Learning Theories	F	%
1	Blended Learning	20	71.43
2	Supported self-learning	8	28.57
3	Collaborative learning	12	42.86
4	Virtual classroom	13	46.43
5	Only face-to-face instruction on campus	2	7.14

Source: Field survey, 2026. (F=frequency, N=sample size).

Result from Table 3 shows that 70.40 percent of the lecturers prefer that if Digital technology be employed in instructional service delivery for Business Education program blended learning model should be adopted. The lecturers also were of the opinion that virtual learning and collaborative learning should be employed in the sandwich programmed as shown in the respective percentage response of 46.43 and 42.86. The respective percentage responses of

7.14 percentage and 28.57 percent show that they had low preference for only face-to-face on campus and supported self-learning modes of instruction.

Research Question 4: What is the opinion of lecturers towards utilizing information and communication tools for instructional delivery in sandwich program in the faculty of Technical and Science Education, Rivers State University?

Table 4: Lecturers’; perception of instructional employing Digital tools in instructional service delivery (N=24)

S/N	Digital tools	SA	A	DA	SDA	M	Decision
1	Digital tools replace the job of lecturers	1	0	2	25	1.18	Disagree
2	Digital tools enhance students’ interest towards	26	1	1	0	3.89	Agree
3	Students might not gain enough via Digital delivery.	3	4	3	18	1.71	Disagree
4	Digital tools to be employed in instructional delivery	18	9	0	1	3.57	Agree

5	Digital tools should not be employed in instructional delivery sandwich program.	1	1	2	24	1.25	Disagree
6	If Digital tools are employed, the students will not be serious in face-to-face in school instruction.	1	1	16	10	1.75	Disagree
7	Using Digital tools erase communication with students and thereby enhance instructional delivery	17	10	0	1	3.54	Agree
8	Using Digital tools make lecturers more productive	21	6	1	0	3.71	Agree
9	Digital tools ease instructional resources.	5	19	2	2	2.96	Agree
10	Digital tools enhance effective use of face-to-face in class instruction time.	6	21	1	1	3.14	Agree

Source: field survey, 2026

Table four shows that lecturers disagree on items 1, 3, 5 and 6 with respective mean responses of 1.18, 1.71, 1.25 and 1.75. The however, agree on items 2, 4, 7, 8, 9 and 10 with mean responses of 3.89, 3.57, 3.71, 2.96 and 3.14 respectively. The summary of these tools to enhance instructional service delivery in Business Education, Delta State University.

Decision of Findings:

Research question one sought to find out lecturers’ level of awareness of digital technology tools. The result showed that lecturers’ level of awareness of these tools is low. The result negates the finding obtained by Adebayo (2022) who found that lecturers were aware of digital tools instructional tools such as desktop computers, laptops, iPads, tablets, Internet-ready mobile phones, Android, iPods smartphones and others. In the study of

Adebayo, the tools listed are hardware tools while in this study, most of them are software tools. This may have accounted for the difference in the level of awareness between the two studies.

Research question two sought to find out lecturers’ level of knowledge on utilizing digital technology tools for instructional service delivery. The result showed that lecturers had knowledge of some of these tools while they lack knowledge of some. This result corroborates the finding of Adebayo (2021) who found that lecturers lack knowledge of how to integrate Digital tools in instructional delivery process.

Research question three sought to find instructional theories lecturers perceive could be used in enhancing instructional service delivery with digital in Business Education, Delta State University. The result showed that lecturers

perceived virtual learning and collaborative learning as models that could be employed for instruction in Business Education, Delta State University. The result of the high level of preference for blended learning, virtual and collaborative learning among the lecturers might have stemmed from their understanding of the benefit such learning model could offer. This is in line with finding of Qasem and Viswanathappa (2016) who found lecturers to have positive perception towards blended learning with integration of digitalization.

Research question four sought to look out lecturers' opinion on utilizing digitalization of instructional service delivery for business education program. The result showed that lecturers perceived that engaging these tools could enhance instructional delivery in the program. This is in line with finding of Qasem and Viswanathappa (2016) who found lecturers to have positive perception towards blended learning with integration of Digitalization. This finding collaborates to the findings of Alassaf (2014), Hue and Jalil (2013), Opatye (2012), Gulbahar and Guven (2008) who all found the subjects of study to have positive attitude towards digital technology in teaching and learning process.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that lecturers in Business Education program in

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Delta State University, Abraka have different level of awareness of Digital tools used in instructional delivery process; their level of knowledge on integrate of number of Digital tools in instruction is low; they prefer blended learning, collaborative and virtual learning theories, if Digital tools to be employed in Business Education, program.. Generally, lecturers have positive attitude towards integrating digital tools in the program.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government owned institutions should organize training for lecturers to acquaint them of digital tools used for instructional service delivery
2. University Management should have practical sessions to equip lecturers with skills on how to employ Digital tools in instructional process.
3. National bodies of Business Education program should be contracted and probably, require their perception on using Digital tools for instructional service delivery in their programmed.
4. Government should provide loan facilities for lecturers to acquire laptops, computers and other digital tools that can be employed in course of carrying out instructional service delivery

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Dr. (Mrs.) Val-Ossai, Marilyn Unonwa and Dr. Edionwe Nosakhare

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